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Assessment of lipolytic activities of bacteria isolated from palm oil processing cottage industries in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Palm oil industry is currently a world leader in the supply of oils and fats which constitutes one of the major sectors of the highest economic importance in Nigeria. This study investigates the lipolytic activity of microorganisms isolated from palm oil processing cottage industries in Ekiti State. Soil samples were taken from a depth of 10 – 15 cm in six different locations within Ekiti State, Nigeria. Microorganisms were isolated from the effluents and identified using standard microbiological techniques and molecular characterization. The microbial isolates were screened for lipase production using modified mineral salt medium in submerged fermentation. Lipase production by the isolates was assessed by halo zone of clearance on nutrient agar plates after incubation at 37°C for 24 hours. The strains of molecularly identified bacteria were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* AE016853.1; *P. syringae* CP019871.1 and *P. putida* JQ782512.1. From this study, the microorganisms (*P. aeruginosa*, *P. syringae* and *P. putida*) isolated from the selected palm oil processing sites display high potential of lipase production. The lipase produced from the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* exhibited high lipolytic activities. The POMEs could serve as source of bacteria for the production of lipases of commercial uses.

Keywords: Assessment; Lipolytic activities; Microorganisms; Palm oil

1. Introduction

Palm oil industry is currently a world leader in the supply of oils and fats which constitutes one of the major sectors of the highest economic importance in Nigeria. The importance of Palm oil in the country is due to the versatility of applications of their by-products, such as cooking oil, special fats, margarines, soaps, detergents, cosmetics, toothpastes, candles, lubricants, biofuels and electric power, among many others [1]. According to USDA [2], there are about five million hectares of palm planted in the world, representing 16 million tons of annual production. Colombia is the first country that produces palm oil in North America and the fourth largest in the world after Malaysia, Indonesia and Nigeria [2].

Most palm oil was obtained from the African oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis* J acq.) and hybrids with other species as well. In developing countries like Nigeria, about 80% of traditional palm oil processing is mostly carried out manually in home and cottage industries, using local equipment and mechanized processors thereby making the process labour intensive [3]. Palm oil processing stand as a major agricultural practice by some individuals in the coastal region. Indiscriminate discharge of many agricultural wastes has resulted in the pollution of environment, affecting aquatic lives and other living organisms. Waste discharged to the environment can be recycled using various biological process. The biological processes in our industries involving the use of microorganisms in the biotransformation of wastes has been extensively used in the production of many products [4].

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Palm oil mill effluent is the final liquid discharge after extracting oil from the mashed, fresh fruit bunch. It is a mixture of water, oil residues, crushed shells, proteins and suspended solids which are composed of plant tissues [5]. One of the main wastes derived from palm oil processing are the palm oil mill effluents (POMEs), an oily wastewater generated from milling activities. Waste discharged to the environment can be recycle using various biological process. The biological processes in our industries involving the use of microorganisms in the biotransformation of wastes has been extensively used in the production of many products [6].

Several microbial species with the ability to remediate palm oil mill effluents (POMEs) have been identified. These include species of *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Alcaligenes*, *Candida*, *Saccharomyces*, *Pichia* and *Yarrowia* have been identified [7]. There are only few studies on the degradation of these wastewaters using native aerobic microbial consortia consisting of microorganisms isolated from highly polluted wastes. Moreover, the use of native microorganisms for the remediation of POMEs might improve the adaption, survival and degrading ability of microorganisms on effluents containing high amounts of toxic contaminants [1].

Microbial lipases play a vital role in the hydrolysis of long chain triglycerides to intermediate and short chain di and monoglycerides, free fatty acid and glycerol [8]. Apart from hydrolysis, lipases are also involved in a wide range of reversible conversion reactions. Lipases are used in the production of food, detergent, pharmaceutical, leather, textile, cosmetic and paper industries [9]. Lipases occur widely in nature and have been found in many species of animals [10], plants [11], bacteria and fungi [12]. Microbial lipases are preferred because they are stable, safe and more useful than those derived from plant and animals because of the great variety of catalytic activities available, ease of genetic manipulation and regular supply due to absence of seasonal fluctuations [13].

Bioremediation of POMEs has been demonstrated to be an efficient method for the degradation of organic pollutants, enhancing the overall degradative performance by using microorganisms with high degradation ability of specific environmental pollutants [10]. Biological treatment has been found to be the most efficient method for removing fat, oil and grease by degrading them into miscible molecules, therefore, manipulation of microorganisms for treatment and bioremediation purposes afford a very efficient tool for purifying contaminated effluents and natural water. The use of lipases (enzymes) that are produced by all organisms may solve the problem, where they catalyze the synthesis or hydrolysis of fat [8]. Therefore, the aim of this study is to assess the lipolytic activities of bacterial isolates from palm oil processing cottage industries in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study Area

The research covered some cottage industries in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The palm oil mill effluents (POME) were collected from six different palm oil processing sites namely (Ago Aduloju, Ado Ekiti (S1), Aba-Medi, Ijan (S2), Aba-Ilupeju, Ijan (S3), College road, Ikere-Ekiti (S4), Sawmill Isinbode (S5) and Sajowa farm, Aramoko-Ekiti (S6) all in Ekiti State. Ekiti State is located in the tropical belt of South-Western part of Nigeria. The sample site descriptors and GPS coordinates (via Google Earth) were recorded and documented in the sample site data collection sheet as 7°25'18.25N 6°2'45.09E. Ekiti State comprises 16 Local Government areas and 3 Geographical zones. Coordinates of the areas where the samples were collected is represented on Ekiti State map (figure 1).

2.2. Collection of samples

Fifty grams (50 g) of samples were taken from a depth of 10 – 15 cm with the aid of soil auger, placed in a sterile polythene bags with appropriate labeling and immediately transported to the Microbiology laboratory, the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria for further microbiological and chemical analyses. The physiochemical characteristics of the samples were determined in accordance with the standard methods published by American Public Health Association [14]. The media used include nutrient agar and MacConkey agar. These media were prepared and sterilized according to the manufacturer's specifications. All the media were sterilized in an autoclave 121°C for 15 minutes.

2.3. Sample preparation and isolation of bacteria

Ten milliliters (10 mL) each of the palm oil mill effluents (POME) samples was collected with 100mL sterile distilled water and serially diluted up to the appropriate dilutions ranging from 10^{-1} – 10^{-5} . From the diluents, 0.1 mL of the culture was taken from 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} – 10^{-5} dilutions, it was dispensed into Petri dishes containing nutrient agar and McConkey agar for incubation at 37 °C for 24 hours.

Figure 1 Map of Ekiti- State showing location of sample collection

2.4. Pure Culture Preparation

After incubation, the distinct colonies formed on the nutrient agar and McConkey agar plates were purified by repeated streaking onto plates containing fresh media under aseptic condition using flamed sterilized inoculating loop and inoculating needle. The sub-cultured plates were further incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 hours for bacteria and 30°C for 48 – 72 hours for fungi. The pure isolates were stored inside Bioroll slants containing about 5 mL of sterilized double strength media and kept inside refrigerator at 4 °C for further characterization and identification.

2.5. Biochemical tests and bacterial identification

The bacterial isolates were presumptively identified by means of morphological characteristics, cellular and biochemical tests. Morphological characteristics were observed for each bacterial colony after 24 hours of growth. The colony of each isolate on the nutrient agar media were observed for identification of shape, appearance and colour, colony size, margin and emulsification. The biochemical tests carried out include; catalase test, indole test, methyl red, voges proskauer, citrate and oxidase. The isolates were identified using Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology [15].

2.6. Molecular identification of Isolates

The bacterial isolates that had the highest lipase activity production were subjected to molecular identification using 16S rRNA. DNA was extracted from single colony by alkaline lysis [16]. Extracted DNA was stored at –20 °C for further molecular analyses. 16S rDNA amplification and sequencing was performed as described by Rahman *et al.* [16]. Primers used to amplify 16S rDNA sequence were forward: 63F 5CAGGCCTAACACATGCAAGTC and reverse: 1389R 5ACGGGCGGTGTGTACAAG in a PCR thermal cycler (ICycler 170-8740, USA). The amplified DNA was visualized by gel electrophoresis and sequenced. The 16S rDNA sequence was analyzed using Chromas LITE (Version 2.01); The most similar bacterial species was found in the GenBank by using BLAST search (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). The phylogenetic reconstruction was accomplished using the neighbor-joining (NJ) algorithm, with bootstrap values calculated from 1000 replicate runs.

2.7. Primary screening of lipase-producing bacteria

The microorganisms were screened for lipase production using the modified methods of Gutarra *et al.* [17]. A small standardized strain was inoculated in Petri dishes containing 0.5% peptone, 0.3% yeast extract, 2% agar and 0.1% tributyrin. The pH of the medium was adjusted to pH 6.0. The plates were incubated at 30°C for 48 hours and examined for halo zones. The halo zones exhibited by each strains of the microorganisms showed their lipase activity with halo radius (R)/colony radius (r) ratio [18].

2.8. Secondary screening of bacteria-producing lipase in submerged state fermentation

The microorganisms showing the higher halo zones were selected for further studies and subjected to submerged fermentation. Nutrient broth was used to grow the bacterial isolates. The bacterial inoculum from nutrient broth culture were then transferred to 1000 ml of freshly prepared mineral salts medium (2.75g/l of K_2HPO_4 , 2.225g/l of KH_2PO_4 , 1.0g/l of $(NH_4)_2SO_4$, 0.2g/l of $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, 0.1g/l of NaCl, 0.02g/l of $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ and 0.01g/l of $CaCl_2$) pH 7.0, supplemented with 1% w/v POME. The medium were incubated at 30 °C on a rotary shaker at 200 rpm. Growth of bacteria was monitored at 600 nm.

2.9. Assay for lipase

Lipase activity of the isolate was quantified as described by Cho *et al.* [19]. The lipase activity was assayed in the reaction mixture containing 180 μ L of solution A (0.062g of p-NPP in 10 mL of 2-propanol, sonicated for 2 minutes before use), 1620 μ L of solution B (0.4% triton x100 and 0.1 % arabic gum in 50 mM TrisHCl, pH 8.0) and 200 μ L enzyme sample. The mixture and the control tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 15 minutes at room temperature 28 ± 2 °C. After incubation for 5 minutes in a water bath for colour development, the tubes were removed from the water bath. Changes in colour to pink indicated the release of p-nitrophenol (pNP) and the optical density of the solution was measured against the temperature inactivated enzyme used as blank at 410nm wavelength (Genesys 20 Spectrophotometer). One unit of lipase activity is equivalent to as the amount of lipase releasing 1 μ mol of p-nitrophenol (pNP) per minute by 1 mL of enzyme [20].

2.10. Statistical analysis of data

2.10.1. Statistical analysis

All the analysis was carried out by using the statistical software package SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 27.0 software.

3. Results

The total bacterial count obtained from POME is presented in Figure 2. Sample obtained from College road, Ikere Ekiti recorded high bacterial counts (6.50×10^6 cfu/mL), followed by sample from Aba-Medi, Ijan (4.50×10^6 cfu/mL), while the least counts was obtained from the sample from Ago Aduloju, Ado Ekiti (2.30×10^6 cfu/mL).

The biochemical and morphological characteristics of the bacterial isolates is shown on Table 1. The four bacteria isolated included *Bacillus licheniformis*, *Citrobacter freundii*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. All the isolates were catalase and citrate positive, motile. *Bacillus licheniformis* and *Bacillus cereus* were methyl red negative, while *Citrobacter freundii* was methyl red positive. *Citrobacter freundii* was indole, oxidase and Voges proskauer negative, but urease positive, while *Bacillus licheniformis* and *Bacillus cereus* were Voges proskauer positive.

Key: S1 - Ago Aduloju, Ado Ekiti, S2 - Aba-Medi, Ijan, S3 - Aba-Ilupeju, Ijan, S4 - College road, Ikere-Ekiti, S5 - Sawmill Isinbode, S6 - Sajowa farm, Aramoko-Ekiti

Figure 2 Total bacterial counts from palm oil mill effluent (POME) from sample locations

The frequency of occurrence of bacteria isolated from the POME is represented on Table 2. Total of six strains of *Bacillus cereus* with (6) 42.9% occurrence, two *Bacillus licheniformis* with (2) 14.3% occurrence, one *Citrobacter freundii* with (1) 7.1 % and five *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with (5) 35.7% were obtained from the POME sample. *Bacillus cereus* had the highest frequency of occurrence 6 (42.9%), while *Citrobacter freundii* had the lowest frequency of occurrence 1(7.1%).

The diameter zone of inhibition of the isolates is also shown in Table 3. The findings revealed that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from Aba Medi had the highest halo zone 38 mm while *Bacillus cereus* from College road had the least halo zone 18 mm.

The quantitative lipase activities screening of bacteria associated with POME is illustrated in Figure 3. The bacterial isolates displayed lipase activity that ranged from 75.33 μ mol/min to 22.44 μ mol/min with the highest enzyme activity exhibited by the *P. aeruginosa* and the least *B. cereus* (22.11 μ mol/min) from College road had the least zone.

Table 1 Biochemical and Morphological Characteristics of Bacteria Isolates from Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME) Samples

Isolates' code	Gram's Rtn	Cat	Mot	Ind	Cit	Oxi	Ure	MR	VP	Colour	Edges	Surface	Suspected Organisms
BAC1	GPB	+	+		+		+	-	+	Cream	Rough	Segmented	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>
BAC2	GPB	+	+		+		+	-	+	Cream	Rough	Segmented	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
BAC3	GPB	+	+		+		+	-	+	Cream	Rough	Segmented	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
BAC4	GNB	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	Cream	Rough	Segmented	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>
BAC5	GNB	+	+		+	+	+	-	+	Cream	Rough	Segmented	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>
BAC6	GPB	+	+		+		+		+	Cream	Rough	Segmented	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
BAC7	GNB	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	Green	Smooth	Smooth	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
BAC8	GNB	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	Green	Smooth	Smooth	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
BAC9	GPB	+	+		+		+		+	Green	Smooth	Smooth	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
BAC10	GPB	+	+		+		+		+	Green	Smooth	Flat	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
BAC11	GNB	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	Green	Smooth	Flat	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
BAC12	G NB	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	Green	Smooth	Smooth	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
BAC13	GNB	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	Green	Smooth	Smooth	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
BAC14	GPB	+	+		+		+	-	+	Green	Smooth	Smooth	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>

Key: Cat = Catalase; Mot = Motility; Ind = Indole; Cit = Citrate; Oxi = Oxidase; Ure = Urease; MR = Methyl red; VP = Voges Proskauer; GNB = Gram Negative Bacilli; GPB = Gram Positive Bacilli; Positive = +; Negative = - BAC1-14= GPB=

Table 2 Frequency of Occurrence of Bacterial Isolates from Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME) from Sample Locations

Isolates	No of occurrence	Frequency	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	6	42.9	2	4	-	-	-	-
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	2	14.3	1	-	1	-	-	-
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	1	7.1	-	1	-	-	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5	35.7	-	-	-	5	-	-
Total	14	100.0	3	5	1	5	0	0

Key: S1 - Ago Aduloju, Ado Ekiti, S2 - Aba-Medi, Ijan, S3 - Aba-Ilupeju, Ijan, S4 - College road, Ikere-Ekiti, S5 - Sawmill Isinbode, S6 - Sajowa farm, Aramoko-Ekiti

Table 3 Primary Screening of Bacteria from Sample Locations for Lipase Production

Isolate code	Organisms	Diameter of Zone of intensification (cm)
S ₁ 10 ⁴	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	2.3
S ₁ 10 ⁵	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	2.8
S ₃ 10 ⁵	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	3.4
S ₃ 10 ⁴	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	3.8
S ₄ 10 ⁴	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	2.9
S ₄ 10 ⁵	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	1.8
S ₆ 10 ⁴	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	3.9
S ₆ 10 ⁵	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	2.0

Key: S₁ - Ago Aduloju, Ado Ekiti, S₂ - Aba-Medi, Ijan, S₃ - Aba-Ilupeju, Ijan, S₄ - College road, Ikere-Ekiti, S₅ - Sawmill Isinbode, S₆ - Sajowa farm, Aramoko-Ekiti

Figure 3 Lipase activity of bacterial isolates

4. Discussion

The bacteria isolated in this study were *Bacillus licheniformis*, *B. cereus*, *Citrobacter freundii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. This finding is in line with report of Odeyemi *et al.* [21]; Ohimain *et al.* [22]; Izah and Ohimain [23] who reported similar bacteria from palm oil mill effluent. However, the high microbial load obtained from College road, Ikere-Ekiti in this study might be due to the ability of the bacterial to utilize the substrate more speedily than the other, the type of microorganisms associated with the wastes, suitable environmental factors and various activities exposing the wastes to more contamination [24]. Also, the bacteria isolated from the palm oil mill effluents might probably originate from the palm oil processing site where there is influx of leachates of water, processing materials like woods which harbours microorganism and human activities. The variation observed in the microbial loads may be due to location, exhaustion of available nutrients in the substrate and the prevailing environmental conditions [25].

The primary screening of lipase-producing bacteria was based on the halo zones around the colony on the plate containing 0.1% tributyrin. The bacteria isolated exhibited varied lipase activities. The zone of clearance around the isolates on the plates could be attributed to the ability of the bacteria to metabolize the substrate in the medium and secretion of active enzymes. Findings on the lipase-producing bacteria have been reported by different researchers [26-28]. The ability of these bacteria to secrets considerable amount of lipolytic enzyme into the culture medium suggests that it can be harnessed for various use both for biotechnological and industrial processes. The production of lipase in

the culture medium in this study is an indication that the enzyme is secreted outside cells [29]; thus easy for extraction during production.

The bacteria isolated from the palm oil mill effluents exhibited lipase activities in submerged state fermentation with variation in their rate of enzyme production. The variation observed in the enzyme activity of the lipase-producing bacteria might be attributed to the source of isolation and genetic make-up [28]. Also, the variation observed in the protein content by each of the isolate in submerged state fermentation could be attributed to the production of variety of hydrolytic enzymes in addition to the enzyme of study [6].

5. Conclusion

The bacterial isolates from palm oil mill effluent (POME) are capable of producing lipases that enhance the growth and survival of the bacteria. Therefore, these bacteria could serve as viable sources for lipases of commercial value.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

Authors have declared that no conflict of interests exists.

References

- [1] Akangbe JA, Adesiji GB, Fakayode SB, Aderibigbe YO. Towards Palm Oil Self-Sufficiency in Nigeria: Constraints and Training Needs Nexus of Palm Oil Extractors. *Journal of Human Ecology*. 2011; 33(2): 139-145.
- [2] USDA Oilseeds: World Markets Trade, United States Department of Agriculture Foreign Agricultural Service, Washington D.C., USA. 2015; 56.
- [3] Awotoye OO, Dada AC, Arawomo GAO. Impact of Palm Oil Processing Effluent Discharging on the Quality of Receiving Soil and Rivers in South Western Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*. 2011; 7(2): 111 - 118.
- [4] Agamuthu P, Tan EL, Shafal AA. Effect of Aeration and Soil Inoculum On the Composition of Palm Oil Mill effluent (POME). *Agricultural Waste*. 1986; 15: 121 -132.
- [5] Bek-Nielsen C, Singh DS, Toh T. Bioremediation of Palm Oil Mill Effluent. Proceedings of the PORIM international palm oil congress, February 16, 1999, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia Bacteria from Oil Contaminated Soils. *Advances in Biological Research*. 1999; 4(5): 249-252.
- [6] Adeleke BS, Akinyele BJ, Olaniyi OO. Purification and Characterization of Linamar's from *Lactobacillus plant arum*. *Journal of Bacteriology and Mycology*. 2017; 4(1): 1045.
- [7] Vijayaraghan K, Ahmad D, Ezani M, Abdul AB. Aerobic Treatment of Palm Oil Mill Effluent. *Journal of Environmental Management*. 2007; 82 (1):24-31.
- [8] Babu IS, Rao GH. Optimization of Process Parameters for the Production of Lipase in Submerged Fermentation by *Yarrowia lipolytica* NCIM 3589. *Research Journal of Microbiology*. 2007; 2: 88-93.
- [9] Gupta R, Gupta N, Rathi P. Bacterial lipases: An overview of production, purification biochemical properties. *Applied Microbiology Biotechnology*. 2004; 64: 763-781.
- [10] Shan T, Wu Reng Y, Wang Y. Breed Difference Regulation of The Porcine Adipose Triglyceride Lipase Hormone Sensitive Lipase by TNF-alpha. *Animal Genetic*. 2009; 40: 863-870.
- [11] Paques FW, Pio PO, Carvalho HL, Macedo GA. Characterization of the Lipase from *Carica papaya* Residues. *Brazilian Journal of Food Technology*. 2008; 11: 20-27.
- [12] Melo LL, Pastore MM, Macedo GA. Optimized Synthesis of Citronellyl Flavour Esters Using Free Immobilized Lipase from *Rhizopus* sp. *Biochemistry*. 2005; 40: 3181-3185.
- [13] Hasan F, Shah AA, Hameed A. Industrial Applications of Microbial Lipases. *Enzyme Microbial Technology*. 2006; 39: 235-251.
- [14] American Public Health Association (APHA). *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water*. 21st Edn. American Public Health Association, Washington, DC., USA. 2005.

- [15] Holt JG, Krieg NR, Sneath PHA, Stanly JT, Williams ST. *Berger's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology*. Lippincott Williams Wilkins, 9th Ed. 1994; 787.
- [16] Rahman B, Kawano S, Yunoki-Esaki K, Anzai T, Endo T. NMR analyses on the interactions of the yeast Tim50 C-terminal region with the presequence and Tim50 core domain. *FEBS Lett*. 2014; 588(5):678-84
- [17] Gutarra MLE, Godoy MG, Maugeri F, Rodrigues MI, Freire DMG, Castilho LR. Production of an Acidic Thermostable Lipase of the Mesophilic Fungus *Penicillium simplicissimum* by solid-state fermentation. *Bio resources Technology*. 2009; 100: 5249-5254.
- [18] Colen G, Junqueira, RG, Moraes-Santos T. Isolation Screening of Alkaline Lipase-Producing Fungi from Brazilian Savanna Soil. *World Journal of Microbiology Biotechnology*. 2006; 22: 881-885.
- [19] Cho KS, Won DH, Cha GH, Lee CC. Regulation of Mst57Dc Expression in Male Accessory Glands of *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Molecular Cells*. 2000; 10(2): 180-185.
- [20] Shukla BN, Desai PV. Isolation, Characterization Optimization of Lipase Producing *Pseudomonas* spp. from Oil Contaminated Sites. *International Journal of Current Microbiology Applied Sciences*. 2016; 5(5): 902-909.
- [21] Odeyemi A, Aderiye J, Adeyeye E. Changes in the Microflora Chemical Components of Domestic Oil Rich Wastewater. *Journal of Microbiology, Biotechnology Food Science*. 2011; 1(1): 126-147.
- [22] Ohimain E, Daokoru C, Izah S, Eke A, Okonkwo C. Microbiology of Palm Oil Mill Effluents. *Journal of Microbiology Biotechnology Research*. 2012; 2(6): 852-863.
- [23] Izah SC, Ohimain EI. Bioethanol Production from Cassava Mill Effluents Supplemented with Solid Agricultural Residues Using Bakers' Yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Journal of Environmental Treatment Techniques*. 2015; 3(1): 47-54.
- [24] Bueno BR, de Oliveira TF, Caliar M, Castiglioni GL, Júnior MSS. Selection Optimization of Extracellular Lipase Production Using Agro-Industrial Waste. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 2014; 13(4): 566-573.
- [25] Trichel H, de Oliveira D, Mazutti MA, Di Luccio M, Oliveira VJ. A Review on Microbial Lipases Production. *Food Bioprocess Technology*. 2010; 3: 182-196.
- [26] Iftikhar T, Niaz M, Afzar M, Haq I, Rajoka MI. Maximization of Intracellular Lipase Production in a Lipase-Overproducing Mutant Derivative of *Rhizopus oligosporus* DGM31: A Kinetic Study. *Food Technology Biotechnology*. 2008; 46: 402-412.
- [27] Odeyemi AT, Aderiye BI, Adeyeye EI, Donbraye E, Faleye T. Lipolytic Activity Molecular Identification of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* *Lysinibacillus sphaericus* Isolated from Domestic Oil Rich Wastewater. *British Microbiology Research Journal*. 2014; 4(4): 392-404.
- [28] Aderiye BI, Adebayo AA, Mustapha B. Bioaccumulation of Heavy Metals and Optimization of Lipase Production by *Lysinibacillus sphaericus* Strain ODE16_EKITI Isolated from Domestic Oil-Rich Wastewater. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 2017; 6(8): 3790-3802.
- [29] Larbidaouadi K, Benattouche Z, Bbouni BA. Screening Selection, Identification, and Production Optimization of Bacterial Lipase Isolated from Industrial Rejection of Gas Station. *Journal of Chemistry Pharmacology Research*. 2014; 6(6): 455-459.